

ELECTROCHEMISTRY OF FLUORIDE SOLUTIONS. PART II. ELECTRODEPOSITION OF COPPER FROM FLUORIDE SOLUTIONS

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The decomposition and the cathode and anode discharge potentials of copper fluoride solutions have been measured at 25°, using polished platinum electrodes. The current-potential curves are normal and show only one break. From the values for the deposition potential of copper, it is inferred that cupric ions are discharged at the cathode. The dissolution potential of copper in the same solutions has also been determined and the metal has been found to dissolve in the cupric form.

Results are also reported on the nature of the deposits on polished platinum and on copper cathodes. Without any addition agents, the deposits are adherent, ductile and fairly lustrous. The cathode current efficiencies are nearly 100%, but the anode efficiencies are always more than 100%.

Additions of ammonium carbonate and of potassium carbonate only serve to make the deposits loose and non-adherent. Addition of cane sugar to the solutions renders the deposits dull. Pyridine is an effective brightener but the deposits become hard and somewhat brittle.

It is concluded from this study that the fluoride bath, when properly maintained, can give good deposits. A limitation of this bath is the low value for the maximum current density that can be used, but the deposits are much brighter than those from acid sulphate bath.

Electrodeposition of copper from fluoborate and fluosilicate solutions has been attempted by a few investigators. Deposition of the metal from fluoride solutions, however, has not received any attention. The present investigation was undertaken with the object of filling this void in our knowledge of the electrochemistry of copper. Data obtained by the electrolysis of copper fluoride solutions on (a) decomposition potentials, (b) cathode and anode discharge potentials on polished platinum electrodes and (c) electrodeposition of copper under a variety of conditions, form the subject matter of this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

The precautions enumerated in Part I of this series (*this Journal*, 1951, 28, 413) for protecting the apparatus from attack by the fluorides were all observed in this investigation. The experimental arrangement and procedure for the measurement of decomposition and discharge potentials were also the same as described in Part I. For determining the dissolution potential of copper, a plate of the chemically pure metal (2.5 × 1.9 sq. cm. in area) was used as the anode. All the experiments were performed at 26°.

Preparation and Analysis of the Electrolyte.—Copper carbonate was added to a standard solution of hydrofluoric acid until an insoluble salt began to separate out (cf. Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. III). The mixture was filtered and the clear filtrate used as a stock solution for all experiments.

The copper content of the electrolyte was determined iodometrically in the usual manner, after neutralisation of the "free" acid by the addition of sodium carbonate until a slight, permanent precipitate appeared and dissolution of this precipitate in dilute acetic acid.

The amount of hydrofluoric acid remaining unneutralised in the copper fluoride solution was calculated from the difference between the initial concentration of hydrofluoric acid and the copper content of the solution.

Decomposition and Discharge Potentials

The current-voltage curves, when drawn from the data obtained, are quite normal, exhibiting only one break, which corresponds with that found in the current-cathode potential and in the current-anode potential curves. The breaks are less pronounced in weak solutions.

The values of the decomposition and discharge potentials, determined from these breaks, are given in Table I. The potential of the saturated KCl-calomel electrode at 26° has been taken as +0.2414 volt (hydrogen electrode = 0).

TABLE I

Solution.	Decomposition potential at 26°.	Discharge potentials at 26° (Hydrogen electrode = 0)	
		Cathode.	Anode.
0.9225M-CuF ₂ +3.2061M-HF	1.33 volts	+0.40	+1.74
0.4538M-CuF ₂ +1.2648M-HF	1.34	+0.34	+1.70

The anodic dissolution potential of copper in a solution containing 0.9225M-CuF₂, 3.2061M-HF was also measured and found to be +0.34, a value which is the same as that attained by the copper plate on simply immersing in the solution. This is significant in view of the fact that copper, normally, though very slowly, goes into solution in hydrofluoric acid.

It is clear from these results that copper dissolves in the fluoride solutions, both anodically and also on simple immersion, in the form of cupric ions and that these ions are discharged directly to copper on the cathode, since the standard electrode potentials for $\text{Cu} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{2+}$ and $\text{Cu} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^+$ are +0.34 and +0.52 respectively.

Electrodeposition of Copper

The arrangement in the electrolytic cell was similar to that described in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The deposits were first obtained on polished platinum cathodes (2.7 × 1.85 sq. cm. in area) and later, from solutions which yielded good deposits, on copper cathodes. Only one anode consisting of a pure copper plate, about 3 cm. × 2 cm. in area and 0.2 cm. thick, was used in all cases, so that, by examining the back of the cathode, an approximate idea of the throwing power of the solution could be obtained.

Unless otherwise mentioned, all experiments were performed at room temperature (26°-28°) and the electrolyte kept agitated. In most cases, the time for the deposition was 45 minutes.

The nature of the electrodeposits from the fluoride solutions at different concentrations was first studied. The results are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Polished platinum cathodes, unless otherwise stated.

No.	Solution composition.	Cathodic current density (amp./dm ²)	Applied voltage	Cathode current efficiency.	Nature of deposit.
1	0.4172M-CuF ₂ . 1.2648M-HF	0.77	0.7	95.17%	Smooth, lustrous, adherent, fine-grained, light pink deposit. Throwing power of the solution was fairly good.
2	"	1.53	0.95	97.01	Deposit was dull red. That at the edges was hard. Otherwise, same as (1). Throwing power was good.
3	"	" (Without agitation of the electrolyte)	1.25	98.79	Same as in (2), but the throwing power of the solution was not very good.
4	"	2.30	1.8	98.45	A few needle-shaped outgrowths were formed at the corners. Otherwise, same as (2). Throwing power was good.
5	"	3.06	2.4	98.79	Colour of the deposit deepened. Small, hard outgrowths at the edges.
6	"	6.12	4.8	99.51	Colour became deeper still. Otherwise, same as (5).
7	"	12.24	6.5	98.93	Dark red deposit. "Trees" formed at the edges.
7 (a).	"	" (Platinum anode was used)	8.2	96.83	Cathodic deposit same as (7). No deposit on the platinum anode—only gas evolution occurred.
8	"	3.06 (Copper electrodes were used)	1.1	88.00	Uniform, fairly lustrous, ductile, smooth, adherent deposit. Under the microscope, it appeared wavy and very fine-grained. Throwing power was good.
9	0.9225M-CuF ₂ . 3.2061M-HF	0.77	0.55	95.40	Deposit was deeper-coloured than (1). Otherwise, same as (1). Throwing power was better than in (1).
10	"	1.53	0.5	97.92	Except for the deep colour, the deposit was same as (2).
11	"	" (Without agitation of the electrolyte)	0.7	98.87	Uniform, smooth deposit. Throwing power of the solution was better than (3).

TABLE II (contd.)

No.	Solution composition.	Cathodic current density (amp./dm ² .)	Applied voltage.	Cathode current efficiency.	Nature of deposit.
12	0.9225M-CuF ₂ , 3.25M-HF	3.06	1.15	99.00%	The deposit was uniform all over the cathode. No outgrowths as in (5).
13	"	" (without agitation of electrolyte)	1.45	99.33	Same as (12).
14	"	6.12	3.5	99.15	Ductile, light pink deposit. Towards the edges, it was dull in appearance. There were slight rounded outgrowths at the corners.
15	"	1.53 (temperature = 50°; electrolyte agitated)	0.75	94.10	Light coloured, but bigger-grained than (10). Throwing power was good.
16	0.1426M-CuF ₂ , 0.5344M-HF	1.53	2.3	97.79	Light pink, smooth and lustrous deposit. Throwing power of the solution was good.
17	"	3.76	5.0	99.68	Darker in colour than (16). Hard at the edges.
18	"	6.12	8.5	—	The top layer of the deposit was non-adherent and powdery. The initial layer was lustrous and adherent. Dark nodules were formed at the edges.
19	"	3.06	1.4	99.90	Light pink, smooth but less lustrous than (17). Slight nodule formation at the edges. It could stand scratch-brushing and could be polished on a buff.

Although the anodes became slightly dark in all these experiments, the corrosion was good and the electrolyte remained entirely clear. The anode current efficiency was also measured and it was always found to be more than 100%, nearly 140-150% in the majority of cases.

Electrodeposition of copper on iron plates directly from these fluoride baths was found difficult as the initial deposit formed on simple-immersion in the solution was rather loose. If a preliminary coat was given from a cyanide bath, however, further deposition from fluoride baths proved successful.

In order to try the effect of diminishing the "free" acid content and simultaneously introducing ammonium fluoride into the electrolyte, ammonium carbonate was added to a solution, having the composition: 0.1742M-CuF₂, 0.5344M-HF. The deposits became dull and somewhat non-adherent in the first instance. When the concentration of ammonium fluoride reached a value of about 0.66M and a current

density of 1.53 amp./dm^2 was employed, an entirely different type of deposit was obtained; it was deep purple in colour and was very hard. Higher concentrations of ammonium fluoride caused precipitation in solution.

The addition of potassium carbonate also made the deposits powdery and non-adherent. A neutral double fluoride bath, containing $0.088M\text{-CuF}_2$ and $0.550M\text{-KF}$, however, gave a thin, adherent immersion-deposit of copper on iron plates. While this thin deposit by itself looked good and could stand scratch-brushing, it was found that an electrodeposit could not be built up on it, as it showed a tendency to peel off.

Effect of Addition Agents

By the addition of cane sugar, the deposits from the fluoride solutions lost their usual lustre and became dull in appearance. No other marked change was produced.

The other addition agent tried was pyridine. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Addition of pyridine.

Unless otherwise mentioned, the cathodes were polished platinum foils, and the current density employed was 3.06 amp./dm^2 .

Original solution = 104 c.c. of $0.4043M\text{-CuF}_2$, $1.9293M\text{-HF}$

No.	Total addition.	Applied voltage.	Nature of deposit.
1.	0.05 c.c.	3.3	Deposit was the same as that without the addition of pyridine. Throwing power of the solution, however, improved a little.
2.	0.15	3.8	Deposit was darker in colour than (1). Hard, rounded nodules were formed all along the edges.
3.	0.25	3.3	Deposit was slightly more lustrous than (2). The anode corrosion improved.
4.	0.45.	3.3	The deposit was much more lustrous than (3). The throwing power of the solution diminished slightly. Cathode current efficiency = 99.3%.
4(a).	"	2.7	Deposit was obtained on a copper cathode. It was even brighter than that on platinum (experiment 4), but it was not ductile.
4(b).	"	1.9	Deposit was obtained on an iron electrode, previously coated with copper from a soluble cyanide bath (this coating being done at a current density of 0.9 amp./sq. dm.). It was less lustrous than 4(a), but as much as that in 4. The deposition was continued further on the same cathode, but a current density of 5.1 amp./sq. dm. was employed. The deposit was now very dull and somewhat loose at the edges.
5.	0.8	2.8	Same as (4). Cathode current efficiency = 99.1%.
6.	1.3	3.2	The deposit at the edges started becoming dull. Throwing power of the solution was slightly poorer than in (4).
7.	1.7	3.2	Dull, ununiform deposit. Throwing power of the solution was very poor.

DISCUSSION

Results given in Table II show that the fluoride baths by themselves give adherent, ductile and fairly lustrous deposits within certain limits of current density, depending on the strength of the electrolyte. The lustre can be enhanced considerably by the addition of pyridine [experiments 4, 4(a) and 5, Table III], but, at the same time, the deposits become rather hard and show a tendency to crack when the electrodes are bent through 180° . The cathode current efficiency is nearly cent per cent in all cases, whereas the anode efficiency is more than 100%; consequently, the solution changes in composition during electrolysis.

FIG. 1

Curves I-III refer respectively to decomposition potential, cathode potential and anode potential.

Potentials given (in curve III) are with respect to H-electrode as zero.

The high anodic current efficiency is rather difficult to account for, as the dissolution of copper, unaided by current, is an extremely slow process. Moreover, as mentioned before, it has been found by experiment that copper goes into solution, either by immersion or anodically, in solutions of hydrofluoric acid, entirely in the form of cupric ions. It appears therefore that the fresh layers of copper continuously exposed by anodic corrosion go into solution in hydrofluoric acid far more rapidly than copper, ordinarily cleaned and left immersed in the acid.

In order to obtain consistent results with fluoride baths over considerable periods of time, particular attention must be paid to two points. Firstly, hydrofluoric acid must be added periodically to the baths to prevent the formation of dull and loose deposits, and also to prevent the precipitation of a basic salt in the solution on exposure to air for a long time. Secondly, the anode-current efficiency being more than 100%, the composition of the solution should be adjusted from time to time.

As compared with the acid sulphate bath, the chief limitation of the fluoride bath is the low value of the maximum current density that can be employed; but, under otherwise identical conditions, the deposits from the fluoride solutions are quite good and comparable in quality with those from the sulphate baths. The deposits from the fluoride baths, however, are vastly superior, both in point of brightness and in retention of the brightness for considerable lengths of time, even in the laboratory atmosphere.

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Received March 13, 1951.

ERRATA

Misprints that occurred in two earlier communications by A. N. Kappanna *et al.*, printed during the year are shown below with corrections.

Page.	Line.	Read	for
284	15	2 HCOO'	2 HCOO
"	18	2 HCOO	2 HCOO'
293	last formula	$2(\text{HCO})_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow 2(\text{HCO})_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2$ $\downarrow$ $2\text{H}_2\text{O} + 4\text{CO}$	$2(\text{HCO})_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2(\text{HCO})_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2$ $2\text{H}_2\text{O} + 4\text{CO}$
415	Below Fig. 1.	Curves I-III	Curves I-II
"	"	Potentials given in II and III	potentials given
417	31	0.37×10^{-6}	037×10^{-6}